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IMPACT OF DEMONETISATION ON GREEN BANKING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UK DISTRICT

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INTRODUCTION

Demonetization is a great step that has been taken by our present Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi by cancelling the 500 and 1000 rupees notes throughout the India on Nov 8, 2016. Demonetization is not only a first attempt in India but it is also takes place in the year 1946 and 1978. By taking this great step our Prime minister has given more preference towards the green banking products. Demonetization is a great concept which comes into existence to make green banking more successful. This action leads to a powerful reaction on the online banking which gives more preference to green banking. So demonetization is a great strategy to create awareness among the rural and urban citizens with regard to the usage of green banking services. Thus demonetization provided helping hand to making green banking more popular. Demonetization has taken a place for the purpose of removing black money throughout the India. So demonetization plays a significant role in the implementation of green banking strategy.

MEANING OF GREEN BANKING

Green banking is ethical bank which encourages the online transactions by reducing the carbon footprint from the regular banking activities. It promotes healthy environmental conditions by protecting our natural resources. In other words green banking means promoting environmental friendly practices in a regular banking activities and it's also called as sustainable banking. Its main objective is to safeguard our natural resources by reducing quality of paper work. It involves online banking, ATM, green credit card etc.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study how demonetization leads to green banking
- To know the usage of green banking after demonetization
- To suggest measures to increase the coverage of green banking.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The required data for the study are collected from primary as well as secondary data. Primary data is collected from using 90 respondents through direct interviews and using questionnaire and the secondary data is collected from journals, articles and websites. For collection of primary data respondents are selected based on the random sampling technique.

LIMITATIONS

- The findings and recommendations of this study collected based on limited coverage only.
- As demonetization is a recent decision, the reactions on green banking cannot be accurately measured.

DATA ANALYSIS

In the current study on "Impact of demonetization on green banking- A study with special reference to U.K district." Primary data is collected through questionnaire and direct interview from 90 respondents. That was analyzed in order to draw certain conclusion in the following manner.

Table: 1 Demographic profiles of the respondents

Demographic Factor	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	35	39
	Female	55	61
	Total	90	100
Age	21-31 Years	20	22
	31-41 Years	38	42
	41-61 years	18	20
	Above 61 years	14	16
	Total	90	100
Education	Primary	15	17
	High school	17	19
	PUC	20	22
	Graduation	23	26
	Post-graduation	11	12
	Illiterates	4	4
	Total	90	100
Monthly Income	0-2000	10	11
	2000-3500	23	26
	3500-5000	-	-
	5000-6500	33	37
	Above 6500	24	26
	Total	90	100

The above table defines the demographic profile of the respondents who are co-operated for this study.

On the basis of above information we can make analysis.

Table: 2 Kinds of accounts

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Saving a/c	68	75%
Fixed deposit	6	67%
Current a/c	7	8%
Recurring deposit	9	10%
Total	90	100

As per as above table is concerned it is cleared that out of 90 respondents 68 are preferred to saving bank account, 6 respondents having fixed deposits, 7 are having current a/c and 9 respondents having recurring deposit. According to this table most of the respondents used to prefer saving account.

Table: 3 Aware about green banking before demonetization

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	70	78%
No	20	22%
Total	90	100

From the above table it is cleared that majority of the respondents that is 70 respondents aware about the green banking services before demonetization and 20 respondents are not having any particular information regarding green banking services.

Table: 4 Usage of green banking services before Demonetization.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Debit card	17	19%
ATM	25	28%
Mobile Banking	9	10%
E-Banking	10	11%
Credit card	10	11%
None of these	19	21%
Total	90	100

From the above table we can see that majority of the respondents that is 17 respondents are using debit card, 25 are using ATM services, 9 respondents are using mobile banking, 10 are using e-banking, 10 are using credit card, and unexpectedly 19 respondents are not using any of the above services of green banking. It says that before demonetization the percentage of using services are very low.

Table: 5 Usage of green banking services after Demonetization.

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Debit card	20	22
ATM	35	39
Mobile banking	11	12
E-Banking	11	13
Credit card	13	14
Total	90	100

From the above analysis we can see that there is that there is a increase in using debit card from 17-

20, ATM from 25-35, mobile banking 9-11, E-banking from 10-11, credit cards from 10-13 respondents. So we say that there is a good effect of demonetization on green banking services. By giving information about the usage of technology we can increase the no of respondents.

Table: 6 Banks initiatives towards awareness of green banking is sufficient.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	46	51
No	44	49
Total	90	100

Above table is defined that 51% of the respondents says the banks are taking sufficient initiatives towards the awareness of the green banking services and 49% of the respondents are feels that the banks are not taking sufficient initiatives towards the services of green banking.

Table: 7 Green banking make banking more convenient.

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	82	91
No	8	9
Total	90	100

From the above table it is clear that 91% of respondents say that green banking would make banking more successful and 9% of the respondents opined that green banking is not convenient for them.

FINDINGS

- This study examines that majority of the respondents having their bank a/c and they use to prefer saving bank a/c to save their money and for the better convenience.
- From this study we can analyze that majority of the respondents are created their a/c before 2014 and they are making regular transactions in the bank.
- From this study we can find that most of the respondents are aware of green banking services but some of them are feels that this system is difficult to operate and not safe and they are having lack of information about the usage of this technology.
- After the demonetization of the 500 and 1000 rupee notes there are great increases in the usage of green banking services. We can also find that some of the banks are not taking initiatives to implement the green banking services among their prospective customers.
- By studying this concept we can find most of the respondents think that green banking

would make banking activity more convenient for them.

- Here we can analyze that in UK district majority of the respondents are not getting accurate information about the adoption of green banking practices because the banks are not taking initiatives in these area to create awareness among this people.
- Finally we can found there is a small impact of demonetization on green banking services in UK district

SUGGESTIONS

- The bank must install biometric ATMs in the rural areas to meet the requirements of illiterate customers
- The bank should erase or remove tax of fee on the usage of other banks ATMs.
- Bank should take up a strong step to create awareness about the availability of green banking services especially in rural areas.
- The bank should arrange seminar, work shop in the rural areas that should be in respondent's understandable language. so that customer can get information and it may create interest among those who did not using green banking services.
- The government should implement new plans and policy for popularizing concept of green banking services and practices.

CONCLUSION

Finally it can concluded that as U.K takes a serious step towards the green banking, coincidentally the demonetization made by the government of India also providing remarkable support to the green banking. As a lesser availability of new notes to the common people of U.K district green banking products are becoming more successful. Demonetization has spread the wider message to all the people of the country about to increase the cashless transaction, where as green banking is totally about to give more preference to cashless

transaction. So there is a great impact of demonetization on green banking services. So U.K banks should adopt green banking technology to create eco-friendly environment. Finally the bank should undertake innovative campaign to create awareness about the benefits available under green banking services.

REFERENCES

- Ahuja Neyati. (2015), "Green Banking in India: A Review Of Literature", International Journal for research in management and pharmacy, Vol.4, January , pp.11-16.
- Amin Ashitha (2016), "Green Banking In India And Global Perspective – A Review", International Journal of Management and Social Science Research Review, Vol.1,
- Bahl Sarita. (2012), "Green Banking- The New Strategic Imperative", Journal Of Asian Research Consortium, Vol.2, Issue 2, February, pp.176-185.
- Bhardwaj B. R and Malhotra A(2013), "Green Banking Strategies: Sustainability through Corporate Entrepreneurship", "Greener Journal of Business and Management Studies", Vol.4, pp.180-193.
- Chaurasia Kumar Ashis(2014) "Green Banking Practices In Indian Banks", Blue Square Publishing House, Vol.1, February, pp.41-54.
- <http://businessworld.in/article/As-Demonetization-Boosts-Digital-Making-Raises-New-Challenges-For-IT-Security-Networking/23-12-2016-110224/>
- <http://m.firstpost.com/politics/narendra-modi-mann-ki-baat-focus-on-digital-payment-e-banking-scheme-3172834.html>
- <http://postcard.news/will-demonetization-lead-digitalization-indian-economy/>
- <http://process.com/blog/2016/11/09/demonetization-high-value-currency-notes-india-big-boost-digital-india/>
- http://wap.business-standard.com/article/opinion/aditya-puri-digital-banking-in-a-digital-india-116032700601_1.html
- <http://www.brinknews.com/asia/demonetization-in-india-driving-a-digital-treasure-hunt/>
- <http://www.credit-suisse.com/us/en/articles/atricles/news-and-expertise/2015/02/en/digitalisation-banks-are-at-a-crossroads.html>
- <http://www.technavio.com/blog/how-demonetization-indian-currency-has-led-increased-use-mobile-wallets>
- Mahesh.A.C, Nirosha.M and Pavithra .V(2016) "Recent Trends In Indian Banking-Green Banking Initiative In India", International Journal Of Science Technology And Management , Vol.5, February, pp.369-374.
- www.indianjournals.com
- www.rbi.org.in
- www.sbi.com
- www.wikipedia.com